

Language and Meaning in Biomedicine - LaMB WG 6 (formerly called Medical Concept Representation -WG 6) (Updated April 2014)

Website of the WG: <http://www.imia-medinfo.org/new2/node/145>

Chair (2012 - 2015)

Stefan Schulz

E-mail: stefan.schulz@medunigraz.at

Co-Chair (2012 - 2015)

László Balkányi

E-mail: Laszlo.Balkanyi@ecdc.europa.eu

Objectives

The (extended) goal of WG 6 is to provide a forum for dialogue and collaboration on the state of the art of research and development in Language and Meaning in Biomedicine. This has been emphasized by the name change. The LaMB Working Group is the international forum for issues related to computer applications and information processing dealing with the representation of meaning in health care and biomedical research, as well as the languages used for this – from natural languages over controlled terminologies, coding systems and formal languages. Since its formation, the working group has been charged with: (1) Reviewing health data terminology and classification needs for the world community; (2) Evaluating information processing technology in meeting these defined needs; and (3) Recommending methods for future biomedical terminology systems.

Recent Activities

- 2014: The leader of the WG, Stefan Schulz was nominated track chair for the track KM-Knowledge management at MEDINFO 2015
- 2013: Joint paper “From Concept Representations to Ontologies: A Paradigm Shift in Health Informatics?” by WG chair & members published here: [Healthcare Informatics Research 2013 Dec;19\(4\):235-242](#).
- 2013: Business meeting at MEDINFO 2013. Report available on the wiki site.
- 2013: On behalf of WG6 on Medical Concept Representation Laszlo Balkanyi, Oliver Bodenreider, Ronald Cornet and Stefan Schulz conducted a survey about the meaning of "medical concept representation", raising the issue of whether this is still an appropriate denomination for the working group. This survey was meant to serve as a starting point for a new scoping of future activities of this WG.
- 2012: Business meeting between Stefan Schulz and Laszlo Balkanyi in October 2012 in Stockholm, from which originated a manuscript which was accepted as a poster for MEDINFO 2013. We expect that around the poster presentation and the WP6 business meeting the discussion will be followed up and a decision about whether the WG should be renamed will be reached.
- 2012: Working Group social media tools established and maintained:
 - The LinkedIn group (http://www.linkedin.com/groups?home=&gid=3680642&trk=anet_ug_hm), administered by Laszlo Balkanyi, the vice chair of the WG, provides a platform for exchange of information and has over 80 registered members to date.
 - A companion wiki site with WG work content and overview of past meetings organized by WG6. (<http://imia-mcr-wg.wikispaces.com/home>)
- 2011: The IMIA WG6 was a sponsor of the International Conference on Biomedical

Ontology (ICBO 2011), University at Buffalo, NY, USA, July 26-30, 2011 (<http://icbo.buffalo.edu/>). The conference was sold out. The proceedings are publicly available at <http://ceur-ws.org/Vol-833/>.

Future Activities: Participants at the last business meeting have agreed on a tentative list of action points: (1) reaching out, (2) meeting reporting, (3) preparation of a WG Workshop at MEDINFO 2015 (4), inquiring at IMIA regarding participation in the relevant scientific program committee (e.g. by nominating an area chair), (5) report the results of this preparatory work till the end of this year.

WG members are expected to suggest (1) influential papers / works / projects to be shared with the community, (2) willingness to host meetings, (3) to host / welcome visitors presenting their work in the domain of medical semantic (4) to suggest the involvement of other parties / industry to WG activities, (5) doing a semiformal survey to collect the data on previously suggested activities